

Original Research Article

Influence of Gandhian Ideology on R. K. Narayan's 'Waiting for Mahatma'

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Abstract

Mahatma Gandhi struggled for the sake of Indian freedom and development. Indian English literature has great impact of Gandhian ideology. The great Indian trio, R.K Narayan, Mulk Raj Anand, Raja Rao has explored Gandhian thoughts in their writings their novels Follow Gandhian and his Principles of Non-violence, Truth, Brotherhood, Satyagraha and views on untouchability. This paper aims at the exploration of some of the Gandhian principles. that later became Gandhian ideology as reflected in Narayana's novel waiting for Mahatma.

Introduction

Mahatma Gandhi became an immense Source of writing and influenced different disciplines and writers from different fields like philosophy, Politics history, literature, sociology, and so on Gandhi is a universal icon of peace. He taught millions the lesson. truth, non-violence and self-reliance. He has influenced almost every walk of Contemporary Indian life. being the reflection of society cannot remain without it. Many Indian writers have written

On Gandhi and his philosophy. There are a few who have recreated Gandhi through historical Fiction, R.K. Narayan is one of the most prominent Contemporary Indian writers have written on Gandhi & his Philosophy. There are few who have recreated Gandhi through, historical fiction, R.K. Narayana is one of the most prominent contemporary Indian writers.

Waiting for Mahatma

R.K. Narayan's waiting for the Mahatma was written in 1955, about Seven years after the assassination of Gandhi. In it R.K. Narayan examines the influence of Gandhi on an average Indian, R.K.

Narayan's novel waiting for the Mahatma covers in Considerable detail the years of political turmoil. Preceding the partition of India, taking Mahatma Gandhi as one of its leading characters.

Like other major novels of Narayan, waiting For the Mahatma is set in the fictional town Malgudi. Sriram, the protagonist of novel is a high school graduate who lives with his grandmother after his Mother and father passed away. Sriram is little informed of the outside world. His immaturity or naivety is apparent in the very first of the novel where he is engaged in conversing with his granny "It's going to be your twentieth birthday, although you behave as if you are half that" ("Narayang")

An occasion he is attracted to Bharati, a girl of his age who is active in Mahatma Gandhi's Quit India movement, and becomes an activist himself for his devotion to Gandhi's political ideology and principles, but for his irresistible attraction to the Gandhian activist Bharati. Narayan seems to experiment with an ordinary folk like Sriram Iyer.

is involved in almost all the major events leading to Indian independence in order to underscore whether Gandhian philosophy was able to transform most Indians.

Sriram, the Protagonist in the novel is representative of the mediocre, middle class Indians with his foibles and faults. It is his Places Gandhi at the only novel which centre of the text William Walsh Praised waiting for the Mahatma "a rare piece of triumph" in which the genius of Mahatma is exquisitely projected.

The Idea of Truth

According to the Gandhian concept of truth,

The instruments of the quest of truth are as simple as they are different! Narayan substantiates this in novels through the characters in search of truth and self. For Gandhi, truth or Satya was the eternal principle of life. He considered it as the force in the universe. It is synonymous to God and amounts to sincerity of heart and inner force of soul that implies. Despite severe heat, the crowd sat patiently and uncomplainingly on the hot sand.

As the Mahatma reaches the venue and delivers his speech "No good. Not enough. I like to see more vigour in your arms, more rhythm, more spirit. It must be like the drum beat of the non-violent soldiers marching behind Mother India.... on to cut the chains that I want to see unity in it!!

The Idea of Renunciation

Narayan is also aware of Gandhian idea of renunciation. Sriram, the protagonist of the novel renounces all luxury and comforts. Gandhi in this novel preferred to stay in a Harijan's hut when he visited the villages. Sriram too feels more comfortable with the ordinary people and asks them not to worry for his stay. His possessions include a spinning wheel, a blanket on which to sleep, and the couple of vessels, some food stuff, and a box of matches, This shows Narayan's keenness in exploring Gandhian life. idea of simplicity in life.

Conclusion

The consequence of deviation from Gandhi's idealism implies the Post-Partition turmoil of religious riots, hunger and unscrupulous politicians. As However, Sriram's portrayal as an ordinary Indian man into a man of self-restraint and self-sacrifice through an eventful journey of self-discovery is quite commendable in turning Gandhi's presence as one of the major characters. in the novel opens up scope for revisiting ideology. Gandhian Ideology.

We reached the conclusion that the testt, though it is a work of fiction, is in fact a mirror reflecting different dimensions of Gandhian chnocaphy ideology at its best. Thus, the avotice has analysed how Gandhi has had an all-pervasive presence throughout the novel. with his dynamic characteristics and ideologies that he employed in moulding young minds such as Bharati and Sriram. In addition, it has brought out the major Philosophical traits that Gandhi preached such as & Satyagra aha, ahimsa, his treatment of untouchability and so on. It has also pointed out his devotion and commitment to his Ideology of non-violence, love and self-sacrifice that would earn him respect and reach him to his goal of Establishing not only a British-Free India but also an India that can govern Belf.

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